

Management Structure

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Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions

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Duration of the project: 48 months

Workpackage: 1 - Management
Task: 1.1

Organisation name of lead beneficiary for this task: CITA
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Dissemination Level: Other

R Document, report
DEM Demonstrator, pilot, prototype
DEC Websites, patent fillings, videos, etc.
OTHER

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1 Management Structure of Innochain

The management of Innochain is organised in WP1. It is structured around four central management boards. The management is cooperative with full representation of all beneficiaries and of the industrial partnership that participate across the four boards.

1.1 Steering Committee (SC)

The Steering Committee (SC) is the highest level of decision making and consists of members from all beneficiaries and representation from the industry partnership. SC is in charge of budget allocation, EC contract agreements and amendments, network agreements, IPR and admission of partners.

It consists of:

M. Ramsgard Thomsen, CITA

J. Knippers, ITKE

B. Sheil, BSA

U. Karlsson, KTH

M. Gausa, IAAC

K. Bollinger, IAO

F. Scheurer from designtoproduction (member of Industry Board).

The Steering Committee will meet at 6 monthly intervals coinciding with key network events.

1.2 Supervisor Board (SB)

The Supervisor Board (SB) monitors network progress, recruitment, synergy across and within the 3 sub-tracks, progress of ESR individual research projects, the training programme, personal development plans and industry collaboration as well as further interaction in and outside the network.

The Supervisor Board consists of the key network beneficiaries:

M. Ramsgard Thomsen (CITA)

Martin Tamke (CITA)

Areti Markopoulou (IAAC)

Bob Sheil (BSA)

Jan Knippers (ITKE)

Anja Jonkhans (IOA)

U. Karlson, (KTH).

The Supervisor Board will meet monthly on web based conference calls.

1.3 Industry Board (IB)

The Industry Board (IB) acts as an advisory board to the SB. It consists of representatives from the industrial partnership who have extensive and successful experience with inter-sector collaboration. It is:

F. Scheurer, Design to Production

J. Runberger, White

M. Fleischmann, HENN

Xavier de Kestelier, Fosters and Partners

S. Oesterle, ROK-Office.

The IB will advise on supporting and improving industry collaboration and will have special focus on opportunities for commercialisation, cross network implementation and further industry collaboration outside the network.

The industry board will meet at 6 monthly intervals coinciding with key network events.

1.4 Work Package Committee (WPC)

Each work package has a Work Package Committee (WPC) responsible for key activities, synergy and progress. They consist of representatives of the beneficiaries taking part in the respective work packages. All committees are represented in the SC making communication

across the WP activities easy and immediate. The WPC will meet at planned training events and when it is technically necessary. Web based meetings will be encouraged.

The Work Package Committees are responsible for the interaction and transfer within the Work Packages. This includes:

- the planning, running and evaluation of the Workshop Seminars which exist as key moments of interaction and transfer within the Work Packages.
- the planning, running and evaluation of Work Package Panels at the Colloquia and final network Conference.

Timing of events

2 The Role of the Visiting Scientist

Visiting scientists have two roles in Innochain. Firstly, they are invited to take part in the Workshop Seminars as invited workshop leaders or seminar presenters. Here they act as central means of informing the project and creating context for the research. Secondly they are invited as reviewers in central research evaluation and quality assurance events including the colloquia, the pre viva seminar and the final ESR evaluation. In this second role they will act as peer reviewers of the individual ESRs and the network as a whole. The network identifies three key scientific peer that will be invited to both colloquia, selected pre-viva and Final ESR Evaluations as means of creating continuity and ability to critically assess the progress and evolution of the project.

The three peers are:

Mark Burry, University of Melbourne

Mathias Kohler, ETH Zurich

Jenny Sabin, Cornell University.